

Bauhinia forficata Link

Family: Fabaceae.

Common names: pata-de-vaca, bauínia.

Origin and endemism: Brazil, not endemic to Brazil

Ecology: Pioneer to early secondary species, heliophilous, semi-deciduous, moderate growth rate (reaching up to 10 m in height).

Ecological importance: The floral nectar serves as a food resource for nectarivorous bats, which are the main pollinators of the species.

Multiple uses: include medicinal (antidiabetic treatments), ornamental landscaping, and ecological restoration of degraded areas. The wood has a low density ($0.66 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$) and low durability, and is used for indoor construction purposes.

Ceiba speciosa (A.St.-Hil.) Ravenna

Family: Malvaceae.

Common names: paineira, paineira-rosa, barriguda.

Origin and endemism: Brazil, not endemic to Brazil

Ecology: Pioneer species, heliophilous, deciduous, fast to moderate growth (up to 30 m in height).

Ecological importance: flowers and nectar provide food for pollinating insects and various bird species. Birds use the floss (natural fiber) for nest building.

Multiple uses: include medicinal (for treating burns, asthma, and coughs), ornamental landscaping, and restoration of degraded lands. The wood is light ($0.22\text{--}0.34 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$) and used in model aircraft, floats, and other lightweight structures. The floss is used as stuffing for pillows and mattresses.

Handroanthus chrysotrichus (Mart. ex DC.) Mattos

Family: Bignoniaceae.

Common names: ipê-amarelo, ipê-amarelo-cascudo.

Origin and endemism: Brazil, not endemic to Brazil

Ecology: Late secondary species; heliophilous; deciduous; slow-growing (up to 30 m in height).

Ecological importance: Flowers and nectar provide resources for pollinating insects, birds, and small mammals.

Multiple uses: include medicinal (the bark contains compounds with antitumoral and analgesic properties, interfering with the DNA synthesis of *Trypanosoma cruzi*, the agent of Chagas disease), ornamental landscaping, and ecological restoration. The wood is of high density ($1.05 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$), high durability, and great mechanical strength, used in civil construction and external structures such as poles, bridges.

Handroanthus impetiginosus (Mart. ex DC.) Mattos

Family: Bignoniaceae.

Common names: ipê-roxo-de-bola, ipê-roxo.

Origin and endemism: Brazil, not endemic to Brazil

Ecology: Secondary species; heliophilous; deciduous; slow to moderate growth (up to 35 m in height).

Ecological importance: Flowers and nectar provide resources for pollinating insects, birds, and small mammals.

Multiple uses: Medicinal (bark contains compounds with anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, diuretic, and antisiphilitic properties), ornamental landscaping, and restoration of degraded lands. The wood is dense ($0.92\text{--}1.08 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$), durable, and resistant, used in civil, hydraulic, naval, and rural construction.

Tabebuia rosea (Bertol.) Bertero ex A.DC.

Family: Bignoniaceae.

Common names: ipê-de-el-salvador, ipê-rosa, guayacán rosad.

Origin and endemism: Central America, cultivated in Brazil;

Ecology: Pioneer species; heliophilous; semi-deciduous; fast-growing (up to 30 m in height).

Ecological importance: Flowers and nectar serve as food for pollinating insects, birds, and small mammals.

Multiple uses: medicinal (anti-inflammatory and healing properties). The wood is of low density ($0.55 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$). In Venezuela, it is widely used in carpentry; in other countries, such as Canada, the United States, and Brazil, it is cultivated as an ornamental tree. Naturally distributed from southern Mexico to Venezuela and Ecuador, and cultivated in the Northern, Southeast, and Center-West regions of Brazil.

Tabebuia roseoalba (Ridl.) Sandwith

Family: Bignoniaceae.

Common names: ipê-branco, pau-d'arco.

Origin and endemism: Brazil, not endemic to Brazil

Ecology: Late secondary species; heliophilous; deciduous; slow-growing (up to 30 m in height).

Ecological importance: Flowers and nectar serve as food sources for pollinating insects, birds, and small mammals.

Multiple uses: include medicinal (leaves contain anti-inflammatory compounds), ornamental landscaping, and restoration of degraded areas. The wood has a low density ($0.58 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$) and moderate durability, making it suitable for indoor construction purposes.

Forest species in Brazil

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